

THEORIES AND DESCRIPTIONS OF EDUCATIONAL METHODS.

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Abstract: This article describes the theories of scientists about educational methods, and each of these methods is given a separate tariff.

Key words: Education, method, person, story, explanation, interpretation, example.

If we think about education, we will first talk about education methods. First of all, the method of education is the way to achieve the goal of education. When applied to educational practice, methods are methods of influencing the mind, will, feelings, and behavior of students.

Educational methods are a set of ways to influence the mind, will, feelings and behavior of students.

Education methods are divided into persuasion, training, encouragement and reprimand according to their specific character. In this case, the general characteristic of the method reflects its uniqueness and applicability. The general methods of education, which are distinguished by the more generalization of the methods, are firmly connected to this classification. It includes methods of persuasion, organization of activities, motivation of students' behavior. In the classification of I.S. Mariyenko, groups of educational methods are named as follows: explanatory-reproductive, problem-based, teaching and training methods, encouraging, hindering, management, self-education.

Methods can be divided into two groups according to the results of their impact on students:

Ethical standards, influencing the creation of motives, the formation of imagination, understanding, and ideas.

- Affecting the formation of habits that determine one or another type of behavior.

At present, more objective and convenient methods are used that reflect the single goal, content and orderliness of educational methods. In connection with such a description, educational methods are divided into three groups:

- Methods that form the consciousness of the individual.
- Methods of organizing activities and forming behavioral experiences.
- It is divided into methods of encouraging behavior and activity. Now we will analyze these methods, that is, methods of forming the consciousness of the

individual in order to form spiritual and moral qualities, faith and worldview in students, to their mind, feelings and will. methods of influence are listed.

It is necessary to train students' ideological consciousness and social activity, that is, the skills of understanding and perceiving the content of the state's internal and international policy. The essence of the methods belonging to this group is that through them the social ideas and goals that have a priority place in society are instilled in the minds of students.

Explanation is the most widely used method in the formation of social consciousness. The task of explanation is to help educate students to have a sense of national pride and become highly cultured adults.

Conversation. The live speech of the teacher is the most effective method in forming the student's personality from an ideological and spiritual-moral point of view. When choosing a topic for an interview, it is necessary to take into account its relevance for the students of this class, the attitude of the students to the content of the interview, and the expected result of the interview.

The story. Students usually listen with great interest to stories enriched with specific examples taken from life and various literature. They can be told stories about people's past, natural resources, life and courage of heroes, as well as moral standards, history, literature and art. Samples of fiction, as well as information published in mass media - radio, television, newspapers and magazines, as well as information published in the Internet press, serve as valuable material for students. Both the conversation and the story should be conducted in a literary language on topics suitable for the age of the students, using words they understand. Determining the topic of the conversation or story by the students ensures their effective passage, as a result of which the students are not indifferent to the topic being presented.

Sample. It is extremely important for students to see and learn from all good moral qualities in the people around them. Therefore, the role of a teacher as a personal example has a great impact, especially on young people. They observe how the teacher behaves in class and in life, how he treats the people around him, how he performs his duties.

Pupils imitate the behavior of people close to them. Attitudes influence the formation of good qualities and sometimes bad qualities in children. Therefore, teachers and parents should be able to restrain themselves in any case. Wherever they are, they should feel that there are children around them. There should be no difference in the behavior and behavior of adults.

Methods of self-education. The process of education can be considered effective only when the student has a need for self-education, i.e., conscious and systematic work on himself. The use of self-education methods in the process of education is considered effective.

Self-analysis (control) is a method of activity aimed at analyzing one's personality, existing qualities, behavior, behavior, enriching existing qualities or eliminating negative habits.

For self-analysis (control), the student regularly writes in his diary about his behavior, discipline, the increase of positive qualities and, conversely, the decrease of his negative habits.

Self-assessment is a method of activity aimed at evaluating one's own personality based on the analysis of existing qualities, behavior, and behavior.

Self-assessment is difficult, but the student can be adequately prepared for it. Therefore, the student must be willing, understand his duty, have a reason for education and upbringing, want to be educated in such a way, see himself through the eyes of his friends and those around him, and should strive for self-development.

To sum up, this education greatly helps to form a person through the methodology.

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